

Kinetics of Oxidation of Phenylacetic acids by Potassium Peroxydisulphate Catalysed by Ag (I) Ion.

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The Ag(I) ion catalysed oxidation of phenylacetic acid and three substituted phenylacetic acids has been found to be first order both with respect to peroxydisulphate and Ag(I) ions and independent of reductant concentration. Allyl acetate, an effective radical scavenger for the sulphate radical ion inhibits the reaction. The thermodynamic parameters have been evaluated. The log k values have been fitted with σ^+ values and the values of ρ^+ has been calculated. The rate laws have been explained on the basis of a free radical mechanism involving Ag(II).

THE kinetics and mechanism of the oxidation of several organic and inorganic substrates both under catalysed and uncatalysed conditions has been a field of interest for several group of workers¹⁻¹². Although the uncatalysed peroxydisulphate oxidation of phenylacetic acid and some substituted phenylacetic acids have been studied by Tanner and Osman¹³, the Ag(I) on catalysed oxidation of these substrates has not been hitherto investigated. In the present investigation, the Ag(I) catalysed oxidation of phenylacetic acid and three substituted phenylacetic acids by peroxydisulphate have been investigated.

Materials and Methods

Phenylacetic acid was crystallised several times before use. The substituted phenylacetic acids were prepared according to the method of Vogel¹⁴. Acetic acid was purified by the method of Bradfield¹⁵. Potassium peroxydisulphate (AR) was used as such. The oxidation studies were carried out in 50% acetic acid (v/v) The ionic strength was maintained at 0.2M by adding sodium acetate. The rate of the reaction was followed by estimating the unreacted peroxydisulphate by the iodometric procedure of Kolthoff and Carr¹⁶. It has been reported by various workers that the Ag(I) ion catalysed peroxydisulphate oxidations of various substrates follow the same rate law both in the presence and absence of oxygen^{12,17,18}. A few experiments were conducted both in the presence and absence of oxygen. It was found that there was no significant change in the kinetic behaviour and rate-law.

Stoichiometry: The stoichiometry of the reaction was verified by allowing solutions of phenylacetic acid 0.01(M), potassium peroxydisulphate 0.02(M) and silver nitrate 0.001(M) to react at 35° over night.

The amount of peroxydisulphate left was found out by the usual procedure. The decrease in peroxydisulphate was noticed to be equal to that in phenylacetic acid within 2-3% in agreement.

Results and Discussion

Peroxydisulphate Dependence: The rate is first order in [peroxydisulphate] as shown by the linearity of the plots of $\log [S_2O_8^{--}]_t$ versus time for over 75-80% of the reaction and also by the constant value of the rate constants over a three-fold range of peroxydisulphate concentrations (0.001-0.003) (Table 1)

TABLE 1—DEPENDENCE OF RATE ON [PEROXYDISULPHATE]

Solvent : 50% HOAC; [Phenylacetic acid] $\times 10^2 = 2M$;
[Ag(I)] $\times 10^3 = 2M$; Temp., 35°; and $\mu = 0.2M$

$[S_2O_8^{--}] \times 10^3 M$	$k_1 \times 10^5 \text{ sec.}^{-1}$
10.0	6.141
15.0	6.146
17.5	6.091
20.0	5.987
25.0	5.980
27.5	5.890
30.0	6.254
32.5	6.250

Phenylacetic acid dependence: Experiments were performed with different concentrations of phenylacetic acid at 35°. The perusal of data in table-2 indicates that within the precision of the results, the rate constant is essentially constant. and therefore, the rate law is zero order of phenylacetic acid concentration.

Dependence on [Ag(I)]: The reaction rate increases with increase of Ag(I) ion concentration. At [Ag(I)] = $2 \times 10^{-3}M$ to $9 \times 10^{-3}M$, the plot of $\log [Ag(I)]$ versus $\log k_1$ gives a unity slope, showing that it is

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first order with respect to Ag(I) ion concentration. Further, a plot of k_1 against $[Ag(I)]$ passes through the origin showing that the uncatalysed decomposition of peroxydisulphate is negligible. The results are presented in Table-3.

TABLE 2—DEPENDENCE OF RATE ON [PHENYLACETIC ACID]

Solvent : 50% HOAC; $[S_2O_8^{--}] \times 10^3 = 10M$
 $[Ag(I)] \times 10^3 = 2M$; Temp. 35°; $\mu = 0.2M$

[Phenylacetic acid]	$k_1 \times 10^5 \text{ sec}^{-1}$
5.0	6.140
7.0	6.214
9.0	6.315
10.0	6.138
13.0	6.414
15.0	6.380

 TABLE 3—DEPENDENCE OF RATE ON $[Ag^+]$

Solvent : 50% HOAC; [Phenylacetic acid] $\times 10^2 = 10M$
 $[S_2O_8^{--}] \times 10^3 = 10M$; Temp. = 35°

[Ag(I)] $\times 10^3 M$	$k_1 \times 10^5 \text{ sec}^{-1}$	k_1 [Ag(I)] $\times 10^2$
2.0	6.141	3.07
3.0	9.594	3.198
4.0	13.05	3.26
5.0	15.73	3.146
6.0	18.42	3.07
7.0	22.60	3.23
8.0	26.10	3.26
9.0	29.17	3.24

Allyl Acetate Inhibition : The rate of the reaction is inhibited by allyl acetate, an efficient scavenger for the sulphate radical ion $SO_4^{\cdot-}$. The results with different concentrations of allyl acetate are presented in Table-4. Accordingly,

$$-d[S_2O_8^{--}]/dt = k'_1[Ag^+][S_2O_8^{--}]$$

where the second order rate constant $k'_1 = k_1/[Ag^+]$. The same rate law has been observed by Anderson and Kochi for the Ag(I) catalysed peroxydisulphate oxidation of pivalic, isobutyric and *n*-butyric acids²⁰.

TABLE 4—EFFECT OF ADDED ALLYL ACETATE ON FIRST ORDER RATE CONSTANT

$[S_2O_8^{--}] \times 10^3 = 10M$; $[Ag(I)] \times 10^3 = 2M$
 Solvent = 50% HOAC, and $\mu = 0.2M$
 [Phenylacetic acid] $\times 10^2 = 10M$; Temp. = 35°

[Allyl acetate]	$k_1 \times 10^5 \text{ sec}^{-1}$
(M)	
Nil	6.141
0.05	1.125
0.25	0.870
0.50	0.310

Temperature Dependence : The variation of the rate constant with temperature is shown in table-5 log k is plotted against $1/T$, and the energy of activation (18.40 K. Cal/mole) has been evaluated. Entropy of activation was found to be -20.00 e.u. for phenylacetic acid,

Effect of substituents on the rate of Oxidation : Experiments were carried out with different substituted phenylacetic acids under identical conditions of solvent, temperature substrate, peroxydisulphate and catalyst concentrations in order to compare their reactivities (Table-5). The order of reactivities

TABLE 5—EFFECT OF VARYING TEMPERATURE ON THE RATE OF OXIDATION OF PHENYLACETIC ACIDS

Solvent = 50% HOAC; $[S_2O_8^{--}] \times 10^3 = 10M$
 $[Substrate] \times 10^2 = 10M$; $[Ag(I)] \times 10^3 = 2M$
 $\mu = 0.2M$

Acid	Temp. °C	$k_1 \times 10^5$ sec ⁻¹	$k'_1 \times 10^2$ 1.mole ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹
Phenylacetic acid	35	6.141	3.070
	40	9.886	4.943
	45	16.50	8.25
<i>p</i> -Methoxy. "	35	9.210	4.605
	40	13.44	6.72
	45	17.66	8.83
<i>p</i> -Bromo. "	35	5.757	2.879
	40	7.676	3.838
	45	13.05	6.525
<i>p</i> -Chloro. "	35	5.35	2.675
	40	7.256	3.628
	45	12.67	6.335

of different substituents conforms to the following sequence : *p*-OCH₃ > H > *p*-Br > *p*-Cl. It is observed that even under conditions when zero order dependence on substrate concentration exists, there is considerable difference in the values of k_1 . The same sequence has been observed by Tanner and Osmani¹³ on the uncatalysed decomposition of phenylacetic acid by peroxydisulphate.

The log k values were fitted to the σ^+ values of Brown and Okamoto²¹. The value of ρ^+ was computed to be -0.3. The correlation of rate constant with σ^+ infers a direct resonance interaction of the substituent with the incipient phenyl radical.

TABLE 6—THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS FOR THE OXIDATION OF PHENYL ACETIC ACID

Acid	E K.cal/mole	ΔH^\ddagger K.cal/mole	ΔS^\ddagger e.u.
H	18.40	17.80	-20.00
<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ .	16.80	16.20	-24.40
<i>p</i> -Br.	19.90	19.30	-15.20
<i>p</i> -Cl.	20.30	19.80	-15.10

Mechanism of the reaction : The above observations are strongly indicative of the operation of a certain chain mechanism involving free radicals. The nature of the silver intermediate in the oxidations by peroxydisulphate is uncertain. Both Ag⁺ and Ag³⁺ ions have been postulated as intermediates. The information regarding the nature of the silver species has been discussed by Anderson and Kochi²⁰.

Recent evidences in the literature point to the fact that in aqueous acid solutions, it is more likely that Ag(II) ions exist rather than Ag(III) ions²².

Gupta and Ghosh²³ have proposed a mechanism involving an equilibrium which is followed by a termolecular rate determining step.

It may be conceivable that Ag(III) is directly involved in the two equivalent oxidation of the acid as represented below :

Such a postulation has been rejected by Anderson and Kochi (loc cit), for it does not allow a ready explanation of the critical role played by alkyl radicals and the catalysis of Cu(II). Further, the value of ρ^+ (-0.3) supports the possibility of a benzyl radical²⁴ and eliminates the possibility of the formation of a benzyl cation²⁵.

The catalytic effect of silver ions may be explained by considering Ag^{+2} and $\text{SO}_4^{\cdot -}$ as the reactive species. This is in accordance with the observations of Subbaraman and Santappa⁴, and Higgenison and Marshall²⁶ that one electron transfer is more likely in oxidation-reduction system between transition metal ion and an ion derived from a non-transition element. In view of the above considerations, the results are best fitted according to the following scheme :

Applying steady state treatment to Ag(II), $\text{SO}_4^{\cdot -}$, $\text{R-CH}_2\text{-COO}^{\cdot}$ and R-CH_2^{\cdot} radicals, we get,

$$-\frac{d[\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}]}{dt} = k_1 [\text{Ag}^+][\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}]$$

The proposed mechanism leads to the observed rate law and explains the dependence of rate constant on the first power of $[\text{Ag}^+]$.

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